

CIR@Sim4IA: Lab Note Submission for Team 1 and Team 2 for Subtask A1

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Abstract

Within this Lab Note, the run files and underlying approaches of the two teams from TH Cologne for Subtask A1 at the micro-shared task of the Sim4IA Workshop 2025 are described. The approaches of both teams were primarily based on three user types, identified by clustering the log files from CORE. In the following text, Team 1 refers to the group consisting of Maryam El Ghadioui and Mark Henri Mörnheim, while Team 2 consists of Timo Busch and Patrick Knippenberg.

Keywords

user simulation, ad hoc retrieval, LoRA finetuning, Prompt Engineering

1. Introduction

This work was carried out as part of the DIS22 project, in which, among others, one group focused on the analysis of the complete CORE log files. Within this broader effort, different perspectives on the data were explored, and clustering analyses were conducted to identify distinct patterns of user behavior. Building on these results, three characteristic user types were derived that form the basis for the subsequent simulations. After preprocessing the CORE log files to exclude bot queries, non-English queries, and other irrelevant entries, a clustering analysis was performed to identify user groups with similar behavior. This analysis revealed three distinct user types: the “Natural Questioner,” the “Moderate Filter User,” and the “Block User.” The Natural Questioner is characterized by starting queries with “Wh”-question terms, whereas the other two user types primarily use the CORE Search Engine’s faceting features or employ Boolean operators to combine multiple keywords. Figure 1 shows an example query from a Boolean Block User, while Figure 2 illustrates the use of common CORE Search Engine facets.

```
("climate change" OR "global warming" OR "climate crisis") AND  
("social media" OR Twitter OR Facebook OR Instagram) AND  
("misinformation" OR "public opinion" OR "awareness") NOT  
("renewable energy" OR "solar power" OR "wind energy")
```

Figure 1: Example query for the user type: Block-User

```
"climate change" AND documentType:"research" AND  
fieldsOfStudy:"environmental science" AND  
(yearPublished>=1999 AND yearPublished<=2006)
```

Figure 2: Example query for the user type: Moderate Filter User

While Team 1 followed the identified clusters when implementing their three user simulators for the task, Team 2 chose a “Basic User” instead of the “Moderate Filter User”, which is characterized by neutral, keyword-based search queries. Both teams utilized the adapted SimIIR 3.0 framework provided by the organizers to carry out the assigned task.

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2. Implementations and approaches of Team 1

For implementing the given user types as user simulators Team 1 used two different approaches, which will be explained in detail in the following subsections.

2.1. Approach for the Natural Questioner

This approach relies on a probabilistic method informed by empirical observations obtained through prior clustering. These observations included, for example, the distribution of "Wh"-query words, the usage of punctuation (29% ending with a question mark, approximately 50% with no punctuation), and the average query length in terms of both words (eleven) and characters (48). Based on these insights, rule-based query variants were formulated for the templates shown below.

```
"{w_word} are the main causes of {topic}"  
"{w_word} can governments do about {topic}"
```

In addition, approaches using spaCy to extract syntactic structures and part-of-speech patterns were tested, but they were discarded because they introduced too much noise while proving less effective.

2.2. Approaches for the Block- and the Moderate Filter User

For the other two user simulators, Team 1 employed a similar approach, using LoRA fine-tuning with LLaMA 3.2 (3B) to adapt the model to the two types of query behavior. Due to privacy concerns when training a large language model on real user data, the students conducted fine-tuning locally, which limited both the size of the model and the amount of training data. For fine-tuning the Block-User, a total of 2,610 "question-answer" pairs were used from the CORE log files. For the Moderate Filter User, 618,654 queries were available from the clustering, but hardware constraints restricted training to a subset of 3,000 "question-answer" pairs.

For training, the keyphrase "Output:" was consistently used as the 'question' marker. The prompt combined the previous query with this keyphrase, providing the model with a simple, structured input from which it could generate the next queries. No additional instructions were needed. The model learned to produce coherent and meaningful outputs based solely on this input structure. During fine-tuning, the keyphrase in the training examples helped the model recognize where generation should begin, resulting in outputs that followed the LoRA-adapted patterns. Accordingly, the prompt for both tasks was structured as follows:

```
prompt: str = f"{query}. {keyphrase}"  
# Example Prompt:  
climate change misinformation wildfires. Output:
```

It was observed that despite the small model and the small amount of training data for both user simulators the fine-tuned model adapted quite well. For the moderate filter user the model was able to adapt the correct structure of the facets that were used in the provided sessions like "yearPublished>= ... AND yearPublished<=..." and while it was hard to evaluate the lower bound of the published year the model clearly learned the upper bound of 2025. Regarding the Block User At first glance, the fine-tuned model was actually using the aspired boolean block structure, while also adding related and meaningful terms, often expanding the query significantly. However, upon closer examination, logical errors in the boolean block structure become incredibly apparent, especially towards the end of the generated response, where the query abruptly ends or parenthesis are plainly missing. As mentioned before, the model is small, yet already powerful, and adds meaningful terms, articulating a great understanding of the prompt and its topics. The real gains will come from better fine-tuning and more training data.

3. Implementations and approaches of Team 2

While Team 1 experimented with different approaches, including a rule-based/probabilistic method and fine-tuning the model on actual user data, Team 2 took a different strategy by leveraging larger language models and exploring prompt engineering. Although the prompts varied for the different user simulators, the overall experimental setup remained consistent. Gemini 2.5 Flash was used via the API to predict user query variations. The prompting strategy followed a few-shot approach, using a consistent set of two example queries from the CORE log files for each characteristic user group. In all three scenarios, the LLM was instructed to generate queries containing 5 to 10 keywords. The corresponding prompts are provided in Figures 3, 4, and 5.

You are a scientific researcher generating search queries for a research database.

Query List:
{queries}

Task: Based on the Query List, write 10 boolean queries that could be the next logical follow up, with 5 to 10 keywords, using AND/OR to combine them.

IMPORTANT: Prioritize queries that are most likely to lead to relevant documents. Order these 10 queries from most promising to least promising.

Only print the queries, do not print any other text.

Example: '(''Social networks'' OR ''Social media'' OR ''networks'' OR ''Digital platforms'' OR ''Peer networks'') AND (''influence'' OR ''Virtual communities'' OR ''connectivity'' OR ''Social platforms'' OR ''Social sharing sites'')'

Figure 3: Prompt instructing an LLM to generate follow-up boolean queries.

You are a basic user generating search queries for a research database.

Query List:
{queries}

Task: Based on the Query List, write 10 queries that could be the next logical follow up with 5 to 10 keywords.

IMPORTANT: Prioritize queries that are most likely to lead to relevant documents. Order these 10 queries from most promising to least promising.

Only print the queries, do not print any other text.

Example: 'Farmers Income Problems in philippines', 'Pierre Bourdieu theory of State cultural capital symbolic capital analysis'

Figure 4: Prompt instructing an LLM to generate follow-up "basic" queries.

You are a basic user generating search queries for a research database.

Query List:
{queries}

Task: Based on the Query List, write 10 queries that could be the next logical follow up, each with 5 to 10 keywords including a question mark.

IMPORTANT: Prioritize queries that are most likely to lead to relevant documents. Order these 10 queries from most promising to least promising.

Only print the queries, do not print any other text.

Example: 'How affect general anesthesia on blood glucose?', 'how did technology change the way students way of learning?'

Figure 5: Prompt instructing an LLM to generate follow-up "natural question" queries.